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Recognizing Foreign Acquired VET Qualifications: Potential to Empower and Challenge Skill Formation Ecosystems

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Abstract

In an era of globalization, demographic change, and increasing academization, recognition of foreign vocational qualifications and credentials (RFQ) has emerged as a critical labor market institution. RFQ promotes mobility, flexibility, and lifelong learning while enabling employers and employees to signal and screen skills effectively. However, comparing qualifications and competencies is challenging, particularly in skill eco-systems that differ significantly. This paper explores the key trade-offs and conflicts of RFQ and how various skill and qualification ecosystems approach this issue. The focus is on Germany, a potential destination country for individuals with VET credentials, and its impact on Kosovo's skill eco-system. The case study reveals that Germany's policies in facilitating RFQ have resulted in new migration-driven VET programs and stakeholder landscape transformations in Kosovo. However, the impact has been mixed, demanding improved joint efforts to achieve positive effects for both skills eco-systems and the mutual benefits of labor migration while safeguarding the sustainable recruitment of skilled workers.

Key words

recognition of current competency, skilled migration, transition economy, foreign aid

1 Introduction

Recognizing foreign acquired VET qualifications (RFQ) fulfils key functions for people, social welfare, and socio-economic development (Cedefop, 2008; Sweetman et al., 2015). Evaluating and validating the equivalence of VET credentials and qualifications obtained by an individual in a foreign country to the qualification in the host country allows migrants to build their career on previously acquired credentials (Brücker et al, 2021; Damelang et al., 2020). It also accelerates migrants' social and economic integration in the host country by improving employment prospects and income generation.

Theoretically, RFQ should serve as a labor market institution that permits the comparison or at least harmonization of qualifications, skills and experience developed in different skill eco-systems (Pfeffer & Skrivanek, 2018). In this context, we understand skill eco-systems as

geographically or sectoral defined social and institutional environments in which skills are developed, demanded, and utilized for productive purposes (Finegold, 1999). However, in practice, the politics and practices that permit RFQ are complex and face substantial conflicts and trade-offs in the countries of origin (CoO) of individuals wanting to get RFQ and in the countries of destination (CoD) that permit RFQ. From a technocratic perspective, these challenges especially arise when comparing institutionally highly different VET systems like those marked by a strong private sector involvement in skill provision with those driven by schools and the state. But RFQ is also salient from a political perspective because RFQ cannot be disentangled from the politically sensitive issue of migration politics. Nevertheless, with the rise of megatrends such as the knowledge economy, academization, demographic change, and the Europeanization of education systems, RFQ is becoming a tool to deal with and resolve new pressures like skill shortages (Hawthorne, 2013). RFQ is therefore evolving to an increasingly important technocratic, but also social and political phenomenon. In view of this trend, in a first step, this paper aims to consolidate the literature to create a more comprehensive understanding of major trade-offs and conflicts that come along with RFQ. In a second step, we empirically investigate the policies and practices that facilitate RFQ in CoO and CoD. Answering these questions will help better understand how RFQ as a labor market institution can empower and limit skill eco-systems, and will contribute to policy debates on sustainable and inclusive migration and education policies.

We apply a qualitative case study design and examine the politics and practices of RFQ in the case of Germany as the CoD and Kosovo as the CoO. This case selection represents a crucial case. Germany has a highly efficient, century-year old collectively organized VET system characterized by a strong commitment and involvement of social partners in VET (Busemeyer & Trampusch, 2012). In contrast, Kosovo's VET system is characterized by a predominantly school-based, centralized, and state-driven system, and a complex history with numerous historical challenges like communist rule, conflict, and instability since gaining independence in 2008 (Pusterla, 2020). Germany has a strong diaspora and positive migration inflows from Kosovo (Gashi & Haxhikadrija, 2012; Hajdari & Krasniqi, 2021), but as an EU-Neighborhood country, Kosovo does not benefit from the Single Market and free movement of people. We concretely compare RFQ policies and practices for qualifications acquired within the construction and health sector. In Germany, the former sector represents a traditionally stronghold of occupational labor protection, collective bargaining and of a long tradition of VET provision (Trampusch, 2020), while the latter represents a relatively new occupational field regulated and offered within the VET track. To support the validity and reliability of findings and add additional context and insight, we will make anecdotal references to the policies and practices of RFQ in the case of the health and construction sector in Switzerland. Since Switzerland is in many ways similar to Germany (collectively organized VET system, advanced and open economy that relies on migration), it can serve as an insightful shadow case (Soifer, 2021). For our empirical analysis, we mainly analyze secondary literature, legislative texts, position statements of key stakeholders, policy debates, and interview transcripts with experts on RFQ.

2 Conflicts and trade-offs in RFQ

As already indicated, in theory, RFQ should serve as a labor market institution to make different skill-ecosystems comparable. In the end, given that we are all human being, it should not be so challenging to be able to consider and evaluate each other's credentials, knowledge, and experience. However, since skill eco-system reflect specific societal and cultural answers to historical problems and political struggles, each skill eco-system and according formalized VET system is historically, socially, culturally, and politically unique, and context-dependent

(Georg, 1997; Wolf, 2011). In view of this, in the following sections, the main political, institutional, and cultural conflicts and trade-offs that accompany RFQ are elaborated.

Firstly, RFQ affects the structure and composition of the labor force and occupational markets in the CoD and CoO. In CoD with highly efficient and collectively driven VET systems like Germany, organized interests like employer organizations and trade unions usually try to protect occupational standards and limit competition from abroad by strongly standardizing and regulating domestic qualifications (Aerne & Trampusch, 2022). Given that a large share of companies train and collectively contribute to the collective good of skills, employers need to be sure that the acquired qualifications are portable between companies to maintain the quality of VET credentials and prevent freeriding (Brown, 2006; Thelen, 2004; Trampusch, 2020). Using formal qualifications as access criteria for positions in certain occupational fields leads to a reduced supply of candidates and creates a monopoly for those who hold those qualifications. This allows to stratify labor markets, fix wages, prevent wage dumping, and essentially maintain the comparative advantage of the skill formation system driving a sector's competitiveness. However, with increasing academization, demographic problems and globalization, which reduce the supply of skills for certain occupational labor markets (Durazzi & Benassi, 2020; Fuchs et al, 2022), this protectionist position conflicts with a rapid social and labor market integration of strongly needed foreign skills to fill occupational skill shortages. Employer associations therefore also discretely lobby their governments for pragmatic and liberal labor migration policies due to fears that their distinct productive systems cannot be maintained (Menz, 2008). The policies, practices, and mechanisms that accompany RFQ therefore need to balance these competing logics and interests by ensuring that the impact of RFQ is complementary and not substitutional to domestic institutional arrangements like collective agreements (Afonso & Dewitt, 2016).

Secondly, RFQ essentially means making qualifications comparable. But because countries have different VET systems, the quality of occupational skills in one country can be qualitatively different in another country. Understanding the relative "quality" and nature of the match between credentials in CoO and CoD is highly challenging (Sweetman et al., 2015). This is especially the case when there are information asymmetries and low levels of trust between employers and authorities in CoD vis-à-vis credentials recognized by authorities in CoO and the actual skills of individuals. This information asymmetry can lead to a mismatch between the "signaling" capacity of qualifications obtained and the capacity of employers to "screen" for employees (Brown, 2001). At the same time, authorities governing occupations, such as those issuing qualification in CoO and those regulating and implementing RFQ in CoD act as monopoly gatekeepers. They do not necessarily have an interest and pressure to have completely transparent, clean, and well-structured processes (Sweetman, et al., 2015). This can materialize in RFQ being lengthy and costly regulative processes and in the creation of incentives to find ways around the process of full RFQ (Hawthorne, 2013).

Thirdly, the RFQ also affects the interests and agency of individuals and their CoO. The right to work can but does not necessarily have to follow from RFQ. This forward ordering of educational credentialing can however have a significant impact on and conflict with the investments into skills and education made by individuals and CoO. Under conditions of uncertainty, RFQ can impact potential migrant's choice of destination and occupation since it increases the information about future employment opportunities in CoD (Czaika et al., 2021). But it also has an impact on the investments decisions of governments in CoO in skills and education: Governments in CoO can view RFQ and potential migration movements as a way to secure cash transfer via remittances, so they domestically orient their skill provision towards CoD' skill eco-systems and undersupply occupational skills needed domestically (Hossain & Hickey, 2019; Ruhs & Anderson, 2010). However, increased migration facilitated via RFQ can

also at a certain point stand in conflict with the CoO's socio-economic development (Docquier & Rapoport, 2012).

This brief overview of trade-offs and conflict that accompany RFQ is not exhaustive. But it directs towards key dimensions that matter for understanding the policies and practices that have been put in place to make RFQ possible. To shed light on these, in the next section, a case study is presented on some policies, practices and dynamics that arose in the case of the Kosovan health and construction sector due to RFQ.

3 Policies and practices resolving the trade-offs and conflicts in the case of the Kosovan skill formation eco-system

3.1 Germany's liberal, but selective migration regimes faced with Kosovo's fragile VET system

Over the last half of century, Germany's migration policies have evolved from being restrictive to being liberal, but selective. Until the 2010s, Germany traditionally relied on the guest-worker approach, intra-EU migration and high-skill migration of ICT professionals to fill comparatively small skill shortages (Maletzky, 2017). These skill shortages were considerably insignificant since the collectively organized VET system was traditionally able to provide the skills demanded by its productive sectors. However, the skill eco-system is under pressure to fill newly arising skill shortages due to increased digitalization and academization shifting the skill eco-system away from vocational skills towards general skills generation, and demographic changes including youth depopulation and ageing (Fuchs et al, 2022). These skill shortages concern a variety of skills and various sectors including manufacturing, construction, and healthcare. Influenced by dominant employer organizations and liberal political parties, two different migration regimes have been put in place to fill skill shortages. On the one hand, Germany has substantially facilitated skilled migration via the adoption of the Recognition Act in 2012 and the subsequent Skilled Worker Immigration Act in 2020 that facilitate the selective labor migration of people with recognized VET qualifications. On the other hand, the Western Balkan Regulation came into force in 2016. It originates in a response to the increase in irregular migration coming from the Western Balkan region to EU countries in 2015 (Bither & Ziebarth, 2018). This act is of specific importance to attracting labor force from the Western Balkans, particularly in non-regulated occupations. It enables workers of all skill levels with or without formal qualifications from the six Western Balkan countries an easier access to the German labor market, provided they have a valid employment contract from a Germany-based employer.

The role of RFQ in Germany's new migration regime has substantial impact on a CoO like Kosovo, which is subject to both migration policies. It is a decisive factor explaining the emergence of a wide range of migration-driven policies and practices in the Kosovar skill eco-system as elaborated below. However, before elaborating on these, the agency of Kosovan needs to be understood. Nearly half of the Kosovan population is considering leaving their CoO to work abroad (Gashi, 2020; Gallup, 2019; Talevska, 2019). Germany constitutes a top CoD. For Kosovars considering migrating to Germany with VET credentials, the pathway via RQF and the Skilled Worker Migration Act is theoretically more sustainable: They have better chances of finding adequate employment that matches their skill level since it makes their qualifications more transparent towards potential employers, they do not have to pass a priority check by the Federal Employment Agency and an annual quota, and they can take their family along (BIBB, n. d.).

But the fundamental system differences between the German and Kosovan VET systems impact the low potential of RFQ earned in Kosovo and the individual agency of Kosovars to undertake the path of «quality seal» (BMWK, 2022) towards a skilled work. RFQ faces

substantial hurdles due to the fragility of the formal Kosovan VET system. The Kosovan National Qualifications Authority (NQA) verified only 111 occupational standards and validated 100 qualifications. The occupational standards, as foreseen by the Law on Vocational Education and Training, have not yet been approved by the Council of VET/CVET because the latter is not operational. In addition, due to limited capacity and resistance from public VET actors, NQA faces obstacles in enforcing the implementation of legislation that requires the accreditation of all qualifications and the accreditation of all VET providers (KEEN, 2019). Public provision of initial VET remains undiversified, school-based, and underfunded, with educational institutions having little managerial and financial autonomy, making VET a non-attractive track. Large differences between the German and Kosovan VET systems constitute a major barrier to meeting the requirements for full RFQ (Gashi, 2021). Compared to other Western Balkan countries, Kosovars have submitted the lowest number of applicants for RFQ (BMBF, 2019).

Despite weak similarity of the two systems, a range of policies and practices have nevertheless been put in place to orient the Kosovan skill eco-system towards the German VET system. This is particularly the case due to the high demand for occupational skills in Germany, especially in the health and construction sector. This includes the diversification of Kosovo's VET by private providers and accordingly increased enrolments in these sectors (Gashi, 2021; KEC, 2021; Serhati, 2017), the establishment of skill partnership models to facilitate RFQ prior emigration, the rise of private German language centers (GAP, 2020) and private recruitment and mediation agencies that process visa applications and work permits all contributing to the creation of a migration-driven skill eco-system (Meyn & Sauer, 2019; Gashi, 2021). This has led to a transformation of the stakeholder landscapes into a complex map that represents a combination of stakeholders in Kosovo and Germany. These include involvement of development cooperation agencies (BPRG, 2020), diaspora organizations, individual diaspora experts who return with government and development cooperation organization support, migration information and advice services, expansion of institutions to address the migration governance, capacity development for labor migration management across various institutions, and, most importantly, private employment and mediation agencies. Two excursions are made into the policies, challenges, and tradeoffs in the health and construction sector.

3.2 Policies, challenges and trade-offs in health occupations

Like in all advanced economies, occupational skills in the German health sector are desperately needed (Flake et al., 2018; IAB, 2022). That Kosovans could be a source to cover these skills is exemplified by the visit of Jens Spahn, former German Federal Minister of Health, in Kosovo, where he visited Kosovan nursing schools and announced that 70'000 nurses were needed (Schmergal, 2019). The German health sector has been addressing the shortage of skilled workers by recruiting care workers from abroad. There were 218,000 individuals with foreign nationality working in the health sector in 2021, of which 36,000 were from Western Balkan countries. The Kosovar health workers' motivation to emigrate remains high, especially due to dissatisfaction with wages and working conditions (Murataj et al., 2022).

In Germany, the health occupations are regulated, which implies that foreign individuals seeking to enter the labor market in this field are required to get RFQ. Qualifications are evaluated against the duration and content of the occupational training. However, there are fundamental differences between the learning content and structure shaping nursing training systems in Germany and Kosovo, with the former emphasizing a holistic approach to healthcare, and the latter focusing on a more medical approach with centralized-education and training. Kosovan nurses often serve as assistants to doctors and perform medical tasks. However, due to these differences, health sector qualifications obtained in Kosovo are not fully recognized without complementary trainings in Germany or Kosovo. In the end, the obtained

credentials are mostly considered different and inferior, so that health workers are usually recruited to provide care for the elderly – a challenging task to otherwise fill (Gashi, 2021).

However, to still overcome this issue of fundamental system differences, the private sector in Kosovo collaborated with German training providers and implemented several measures as part of their adjustment programs. The dual-track Bachelor study initiated by a German benchmarked but national private higher education institution (hereinafter referred to as “college”) in Pristina adapted German curricula to Kosovar labor market needs and reality. The first step involved creating an educational track that combined the practical aspects of the German dual system with the academic requirements of a Bachelor's program following the Bologna system, which is recognized in both countries. Furthermore, certain fields of study that were lacking in the Kosovar system were introduced in the curricula, such as social law, documentation and quality assurance” (Sauer & Volarevic, 2020). To further meet the demands of the German labor market, the college partnered with German hospitals and undertook other additional steps to create the adjustments in curricula, such as facilitating teacher/trainer and student mobility within the German market. Moreover, qualifications that were portable between private health corporations and private universities were initiated, which contributed to a rise of bilateral standard-settings. These private-sector generated models claim to prepare candidates for the “home track” (those planning to stay in CoC) and the “away track” (those that seek work in the CoD Germany). Provision of similar, yet different models emerged from other private higher education institutions. The health qualifications rapidly became a common path among youth – mainly female entrants of the higher education level.

3.3 Policies, challenges, and trade-offs in construction occupations

The Western Balkan regulation has been especially attractive to attract low-skill workers without formal qualifications from Western Balkan countries, including Kosovo. For example, in 2017 42% of pre-approvals came from the construction sector (Bither & Ziebarth, 2018). However, German embassies in certain Western Balkan Countries such as Kosovo still carried out rigorous plausibility assessment during the visa application process for individuals seeking to work in non-regulated professions like the construction sector. “A bricklayer without a qualification” was regularly rejected (BMAS, 2020, p. 116). In response, short courses provided by vocational training centers offered by public employment services gained momentum. One third of Kosovan youth are not in education, employment or training (World Bank, 2022). For a Kosovar lacking an official certificate but with significant work experience, one of the most feasible “short-cut” solutions is to undertake a three-month training and/or examination. Short-term courses offered by vocational training centers were the most popular among all Active Labour Market Measures (ALMM): a significant number of individuals utilized these courses, with the highest number of beneficiaries (6,736) recorded in 2016 (KEEN, 2019). In light of this example, experts find that as a response to Germany’s evolving demand for skilled labor, prospective Kosovar migrants are motivated to obtain higher qualifications, resulting in a strengthened human capital stock (Vracic, 2018).

Under the lead of the Ministry of Labour and Social Welfare of Kosovo and in cooperation with a German development cooperation agency and German employer organization, “Skills Partnership Program” were established with the goal of enhancing the standard of vocational education in the Kosovan construction sector. This provided young Kosovars the opportunity to undertake a 2 to 3-year dual training course in the member companies of the German construction organizations. A goal of this partnership was to equip the potential workforce for CoD by offering them initial language skills, career counseling and information, assistance with the recruitment process while still in their country of origin, as well as cultural preparation both before and after they reached the CoD through an Albanian Diaspora organization. Such partnerships are coined as “transnational skills partnerships” and aspire a mobility “platform”

that aims to define benefits of all actors involved (Azahaf, 2020; Clemens, 2015; Sauer, & Klllokoqi: 2017). The enrolment in apprenticeship program in Germany requires no recognition of previous qualifications. This makes it an appealing option for Kosovars seeking both employment and training opportunities, particularly since apprenticeships are typically compensated, with employers offering monthly salaries and opportunities for further training. For Germany, this group of apprentices – prospective labor force – implies filled gaps in the economy.

As a result of increased levels of trust built within the cooperation in the Skills Partnership Scheme in construction occupations, another, though more cooperative-intensive initiative came along. A German employer organization initiated the harmonization of occupational standards for “bricklayer”, which required the involvement of wider range of stakeholders consisting of both the public and private institutions in Kosovo and Germany. Despite difficulties, the initiative succeeded in convening a comprehensive group of decision-makers and stakeholders, such as a German chamber of commerce, the Kosovar Agency of VET, a Kosovar VET upper-secondary school offering qualifications in construction, and one of the largest Kosovo-based local employer organizations in the construction sector. The cooperation resulted in development of a new occupational standard getting verified and validated by both the Kosovar and German quality assurance and recognition authorities. Subsequently, curricula were developed to align with the new occupational standard.

These partnership schemes were successful in paving the way to RFQ relevant initiatives, such as the above-mentioned harmonization of occupational standards and curricula to approximate the qualifications between involved countries in the partnership. Within the construction industry alone, approximately 10 new institutions and 20 new training profiles were established between the years 2016 and 2019. The accreditation and validation by the National Qualifications Authority of the majority of programmes followed shortly after their establishment (NQA, 2016, 2019). However, such initiatives do not influence the system level of the VET system, hence the positive spillover effects in the Kosovan skill eco-system remains limited.

3.4 Implications for Kosovo’s skill eco-system

The new migration regime in Germany governed by full or partial RQF has contributed to an increase in private providers, vocational training modules and program of different formats within the Kosovan VET system. Migration policies in the CoD have transformed the stakeholder landscape in the CoO, primarily in the health and construction sector. Yet, the question must be raised whether these new developments add complementary or substitutional value and if they empower or challenge the Kosovan skill eco-system. The synergies between Germany’s policies on the one hand and the practices in Kosovo on the other hand are not being reflected and mainstreamed in the public policies within Kosovo. They remain pilots and projects with less potential for scale-up within the Kosovan system. And although all these initiatives aim at harmonizing the Kosovan with the German VET system, post-implementation feedback from involved stakeholders and experts perceive this objective as not feasible in view of the fundamental system differences between the two VET systems.

It is furthermore unclear if these developments signify an authentic expansion of vocational education and training options or if they reflect a business model and profit-driven strategy that depletes the pool of skilled workers in Kosovo (Gashi, 2021). Proxy indicators on increased enrollments in health and construction in Kosovo lead to the anecdotal assumption that Kosovar youth make education and training choices driven by the demands in Germany more than those in their home country, “increasing competition in the same sectors [at home]” (Vracic, 2018, n. p.). Kosovo with its ageing population faces a high risk of youth drain in general, and brain drain among its health and medical professionals in particular (Ahmetxhekaj, 2019; Gashi,

2021). Although the World Health Organization recommends that developed countries facing labor shortages should not actively recruit health workers from countries experiencing critical shortages (WHO, 2021), private institutions and providers offering new health programs, as well as licensed recruitment and employment agencies can pursue their business plans without being subject to any accountability or monitoring system. Seeking employment via private agencies is frequently the only choice for obtaining legitimate employment for many individuals, but it is also the most rapid route to becoming employed irregularly (Lakić, 2023). And there remains a lack of monitoring and evaluation mechanisms for example by labor inspectors that would safeguard ethical and orderly standards of recruitment abroad. Dubious narratives have been massively reported in the last five years (Correctiv, 2020; Lakić, 2023).

3.5 Swiss RFQ policies and practices for skills developed in Kosovo: Irrelevant due to lack of forward ordering of educational credentialing

Despite having a similar VET system marked by strong involvement of social partners, similar relative size of components of the economy, and similarly high reliance on foreign skills, Switzerland's policies and practices with regards to RFQ differ substantially. Foreign VET qualifications are mainly recognized and regulated for safety concerns, and they do not ensure forward ordering of educational credentialing like in the case of Germany. For example, nurses within the health sector and specific professions in the construction sector like crane operator are primarily recognized by state and cantonal authorities (SERI, n.d., 2022). Employer or professional organizations do not have any relevant discretionary power. Employer and professional organizations are however free to RFQ independently of national regulations, but they usually only do so for a limited number of CoO, for example neighboring countries with similar VET systems (Aerne & Trampusch, 2022). Since RFQ does not ensure forward ordering of educational credentialing because RQF and labor migration policies are not connected like in the case of Germany, RQF plays a very limited role as a labor market institution. Moreover, Switzerland follows a more restrictive policy towards labor migration from non-EU countries, regulated by a quite strict quota system directed at high skill professionals like IT experts (Lavenex & Manatschal, 2022). Therefore, Swiss RQF policies and practices do not systematically impact individuals with VET credentials and stakeholders' landscapes in a non-EU CoO like Kosovo.

These differences in RFQ policies and practices can likely be explained by the fact that Switzerland is able to attract foreign skills via intra-EU migration due to its relatively high average wages, an education system that still primarily relies on a strong VET system compared to Germany (Durazzi & Benassi, 2020), and the relatively smaller size of the economy. This weak appetite for low- and mid-level skill migration and protected occupational labor markets, but liberal high-skills migration represents a typical strategy employed by economies with collectively provided skill eco-systems (Menz, 2008).

4 Conclusion and policy recommendations

In conclusion, our analysis demonstrates the challenges and opportunities of using RFQ as a labor market institution for governing labor mobility and emigration from CoO like Kosovo to CoD like Germany. The RFQ presents a significant obstacle for Kosovans considering Germany as a work destination, particularly in regulated occupations like health, which are subject to RFQ and deemed fundamentally different and incomparable between the two countries. Migration-driven policies need to be considered in conjunction with VET policies and dynamics in the CoO to achieve effective integration of skilled migrants into the CoD's labor market. Partnership-based initiatives among public and private representatives are essential for enabling reciprocal trust in institutions, among gatekeepers of occupational markets, and for enabling trade-offs and bringing the practice of RFQ into life.

The research has shed light into the importance of effective policies for managing labor migration to facilitate the integration of emerging stakeholders, enable the creation of monitoring mechanisms among them and their migration-driven activities, while also promoting the scaling up of initiatives that generate positive spill-over effects in specific qualifications. However, to maintain the credibility of regular labor migration channels the coordination processes and mandates of various stakeholders need to be improved. This includes improved transparency and communication to limit misinformation spread by private and shady recruitment agencies and to better manage expectations of individuals and governments in CoO. Moreover, the labor market and development implications both in the CoD and the CoO need to be considered, for example, regarding brain drain in the health sector or implications for the German VET system. As long as wealthy nations continue to require labour and have the capacity to attract workers from developing countries, it is unlikely that they will alter their migration policies in the near future. Acknowledging this is important to understand the implications of immigration of these countries for vulnerable countries like Kosovo, to identify the favorable outcomes and strategies, and alleviate unfavorable consequences (Vracic, 2018).

By implementing these policy recommendations, we believe that Germany and Kosovo can both strengthen their entire skill eco-systems, foster development, and ultimately achieve the mutual benefits of labor migration while safeguarding the ethical recruitment of skilled workers.

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